

3D Conceptual Design and Planning of Race Track in Kerala

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Abstract: *The number of track-based bikes being manufactured is increasing day by day. New manufactures as well as existing companies are racing against each other in the battle of making their bikes faster as well as technology enabled but on the other hand the roads of Kerala at present are not equipped to handle these types of specially made vehicles. As a result, the number of youths getting killed due to road accidents increased, the reasons for crashes are mostly overspeed, and adventurous activities. This has become a social issue that needs to be addressed, so considering the social and ethical responsibility of an engineer the plan to devise a race track that was curated for Kerala audience was made. As a part of this idea a decision was made to adopt new methodology incorporating most of the advancements in civil engineering, rather than opting conventional building design methods. This meant the incorporation of technologies like AI, VR, AR, GIS and other modern methods.*

Keywords: AI, VR, GIS, Revit

1.Introduction

The number of youths getting killed in bike accidents due to careless and rash driving has increased exponentially after the track-oriented bikes were made available in the domestic market. Less number of people are addressing this issue and even if these types of news reports get attention strict laws are being reinforced unnecessarily which affects the innocent day to day drivers and general public. A senior police official once recommended that manufacturers should limit the speed of these vehicles but that is certainly not the most advisable method. To resolve this issue the proposal for a track, a place where all these adventurous activities can be safely performed, is put forward. Now the authority can advise the youth, guide them to carry out their shenanigans on the race circuit. There is an added benefit of creating a youth passionate about a sport that is widely popular around the world, training could be carried out at grassroot levels, incorporation of motorsport related industries their growth and development will lead to a financial development and growth of economy.

2.Materials and Methodology

The methodology used throughout in this project is a self-devised one as there was a need to incorporate most modern technologies, as a result, the idea of project development used here was decided to shift from traditional approach to more modern approach which incorporates the use of technologies such as Artificial intelligence, Virtual reality, Augmented reality, Building information modeling, Geographical information system etc. There has been the involvement of the general public in the study during the early stages mostly during the feasibility studies, and the public opinion signifies the need as they both agree to this idea and offered support to develop. This project not only aims to prepare reports and carry out surveys but also create visualization techniques and models which can be used for making this idea into a business proposal.

2.1Pre-Project Phase: The project starts budding at this stage, the pre-project planning phase includes the development of the concept of the project, including the basic decision of selecting the concept that will be used for the execution of work. The idea of work, the strategies to be adopted etc. are discussed here. This stage is often split into: **Idea/Initiation Phase:** This phase aims to identify all possible projects based on examination of needs and the possible options. Any basic idea that addresses societies needs are mostly unlikely to fail given that the solution is admissible and technically feasible. The need of the society was to address the issue of rash driving and over speeding among the youth, due to the fact that conventional methods like traffic rules have failed to eradicate this issue the idea to create a designated sport out of this popped up into the mind.

Project Concept phase: In this phase as many project concepts possible are identified and using some selection procedure, some concepts are selected. Greatest degree of uncertainty about the future is encountered. Selected ones used as inputs for the feasibility phase. For this project there was a need to

choose from a wide range of track grades (Grade A, B, C etc.), where each of them differed in terms of cost of construction to the types of races they could host. So, to choose from these based on the feasibility analysis, that was done in the initial phase and the correct concept was selected. **Feasibility Phase:** In this phase analysis carried out through survey methods, the convenience of Google forms has been utilized and topic related questionnaires were sent out. To ensure this was reaching the correct audience circulation medium was prior fixed like the use of showroom-based surveys to existing customers and potential customers through social media facilitated in getting more accurate and reliable results.

2.2 Project Phase:

This is the phase where the abstract idea of the project moves further into the execution stage where the designs required are prepared and the steps are taken for the implementation of the project. There arise various dependencies in this phase, this could alter the work pattern or even change the flow of work. The various steps included in this stage are: Basic design phase: An outline of the desired idea is prepared, a preliminary drawing here it was created with the help of Artificial Intelligence and Machine learning. Several datasets were provided to the AI to act as a reference for the creation of a unique drawing. This drawing was a result of huge computations which took several hours to complete.

Detailed design phase: This phase includes the drawings both architectural, structural, estimates etc. which needs to be prepared. For this project due to the time constraints and also due to insufficient resources, there was only provision for the completion of architectural drawings. Nevertheless, geographical analysis is carried out which is essentially unique. Due to the fact that the project was developed using Building Information Modelling (BIM) it is further helpful and comparatively easy to extract entities like estimates based on the structural and architectural drawings that were prepared.

Tendering phase: Includes preparing specifications and agreement conditions, preparing bill of quantities and estimating the contract value This project usually demands a team of experts in architectural, civil engineering fields as it involves close calculations done in both transportation and geotechnical disciplines. Usually, companies with similar experience like The Driven Intl. Ltd. Provides more reliability rather than other inexperienced agencies. Execution/construction Phase: This phase begins immediately after the contract is awarded as the contract is a time bound agreement and it is a necessity. Progress of work is closely monitored with the contractor to assess cost and schedule. Corrective measures are made whenever suitable.

Closure / Completion phase: The circuit is tested and commissioned; this is usually done by certain regulating authorities. Usually for Motorsport events based on bikes the authority is Fédération International de Motorcycles (FIM) which is a French body that regulates events related to MotoGP events. After the inspection a certain license would be provided which is a designation on which class of Grand prix event they can host.

2.3 Post Project Phase

This phase is also termed as the 'Turn over' phase. At this stage the responsibility is transferred from engineers / contractors to the owners, where they are responsible to maintain the quality standards as well as ensure proper facilities such as drainage. During this phase the damaged/expired safety equipment needs to be replaced also the FIM license should be renewed every 3 years.

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Feasibility Analysis: What type of motorcycle do they own?

For this there were options to choose from of the major track-based motorcycle manufacturers. The range included from KTM, Yamaha, Kawasaki to non-track-based brands like Royal Enfield, Hero etc. There were 807 KTM users, 771 Yamaha users, 604 Bajaj users etc. (Figure1) Which signifies that the data we collected is valid as these were the intended racing group. District/ City you live in?

This data was collected in order for us to get spatial information in terms of geographical location to determine where the location would be most feasible. The results indicated that the survey population was distributed all across the geography of Kerala. Trivandrum being the highest contributed more than 25%, Ernakulam being second had 20.7% of the population

Figure .1 Motorcycle owned and Location of Users

a) Have you heard of Motorsport racing?

This provides us with a brief idea about the people incorporated in this study, as the results indicate 90.3% of people who participated in our study had said they were familiar with the term motorsport racing. This means only 9.7% of the data we received would be inadmissible.

Figure2. a) heard of Motorsport racing, b) Is it a track-based bike c) Are you interested in Motorsport racing d) How often would you use the track

b) Is it a track-based bike?

This question signifies our potential customers as every single bike that is meant for the road cannot simply be accommodated on a track as we need specific bikes, cars which are made as per track requirements which are so called track-based vehicles. In olden days track bikes were modified versions of street legal bikes whereas now manufacturers create a track-based bike which is further modified to meet legal specifications. These numbers could essentially be our future customers as they might have bought these bikes for the same purpose.

c) Are you interested in Motorsport racing?

As the results indicate here the majority are interested in motorsport racing, there might be people included who are interested in racing but don't own a track-based bike but there isn't any method specified in google forms to filter out this category.

Do you currently have a track license/ Are you planning to apply for track license:

This determines potential usage of our track, as a person for owning a track license needs to meet certain

prerequisites which can only be met on a track and even after getting the track license he/she doesn't stop using the track they become one among frequent users. From the survey 99.5% of the people said they don't own a license which is expected but 26% were planning to take a license and of the 58.6% who are not sure whether to take one or not (Fig 5.2.9), with proper guidance we could influence a chunk of people to take one.

Figure 3. a) Can you describe your interest in this field b) Do you currently own a track license c) Are you planning to apply for track license d) your opinion about developing a track in Kerala

3.2 Different Technologies applied in design

AI systems work by ingesting large amounts of labeled training data, analyzing the data for correlations and patterns, and using these patterns to make predictions about future states. In this way, a chatbot that is fed examples of text chats can learn to produce lifelike exchanges with people, or an image recognition tool can learn to identify and describe objects in images by reviewing millions of examples.

Modeling the project using Revit: A flat terrain was assumed for modelling and with the help of site and massing tools, the surface required was modeled. The circuit layout was based on the previous results of the Ai phase, nevertheless there were limitations in that layout and human intervention was necessary. The track was developed keeping in mind the feasibility and the requirement criteria so in order to balance this a multipurpose circuit design was devised. This aided the use of different parts of the tracks for different uses such as for carting, drag racing etc.

A Geographic Information System software (GIS Software) is designed to store, retrieve, manage, display, and analyze all types of geographic and spatial data. GIS software lets you produce maps and other graphic displays of geographic information for analysis and presentation. These software's depending upon the platform which they are run on brings several items to the table, they also range from software's that are open source, licensed and also others which are free for research uses.

Augmented reality (AR) is an enhanced version of the real physical world that is achieved through the use of digital visual elements, sound, or other sensory stimuli delivered via technology. It is a growing trend among companies involved in mobile computing and business applications in particular. Virtual Reality (VR) is the use of computer technology to create a simulated environment. Unlike traditional user interfaces, VR places the user inside an experience. Instead of viewing a screen in front of them, users are immersed

and able to interact with 3D worlds.

Figure.4 REVIT Model of Race Track

4. Conclusion: A part of this project the current state of road accidents in Kerala was analyzed and it was found out that the accidents due to performance enhanced motorbikes were increasing day by day. The methods implemented now to eradicate this issue had not yet achieved a huge success rate, thus to fulfil the need this study proposes a development of catered race track. The feasibility studies indicate that people support these types of projects and not just any type of people but potential customers were narrowed down. Although there was a need for a track, the study indicated that it was not for a Grade A circuit, rather it was for an economically viable track. To fit this purpose a multipurpose track was devised where a number of racing events can be hosted. The preliminary design phase involved the use of Ai as an inspiration, it was trained with previous models and datasets and later could produce very realistic outputs and the design was done on Revit which is a BIM based software so that any further development in the project can be modeled with ease. These models were then converted to walkthroughs and were rendered to get more realistic views. To top it all off these were converted into VR and AR formats as these are very easy to visualize and perceive. The next stage of development meant narrowing down to a potential location as of where in Kerala, so to do it scientifically, the use of GIS was incorporated and with the help of ArcGIS software and the data from sites like BHUVAN, NASA, ESRI etc. study area maps were prepared for gaining more idea.

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